

MATRYCS

D8.2 | MATRYCS Website

WP8 – Communication, Dissemination
and Awareness Creation

February 2021

www.matrycs.eu

Modular Big Data Applications for Holistic Energy Services in Buildings

MATRYCS

Disclaimer

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the EASME nor the European Commission is responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Copyright Message

This report, if not confidential, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0); a copy is available here: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. You are free to share (copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format) and adapt (remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially) under the following terms: (i) attribution (you must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made; you may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use); (ii) no additional restrictions (you may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits).

The MATRYCS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no.101000158

Grant Agreement Number	101000158		Acronym	MATRYCS
Full Title	Modular Big Data Applications for Holistic Energy Services in Buildings			
Topic	LC-SC3-B4E-6-2020 Big data for buildings			
Funding scheme	H2020- IA: Innovation Action			
Start Date	October 2020	Duration	36	
Project URL	www.matrycs.eu			
Project Coordinator	ENG			
Deliverable	D8.2- MATRYCS Website			
Work Package	WP8-Communication, Dissemination and Awareness Creation			
Delivery Month (DoA)	M5	Version	1.0	
Actual Delivery Date	26/02/2021			
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public	
Lead Beneficiary	HOLISTIC			
Authors	Zoi Mylona [HOLISTIC]			
Quality Reviewer(s):	Diana Yordanova [HOUSING EUROPE], Jaime Gómez Tribiño [VEOLIA]			
Keywords	Website, Design, Website map, Online presence, Social media			

Preface

MATRYCS focuses on addressing emerging challenges in big data management for buildings with an **open holistic solution** for Business to Business platforms, able to give a competitive solution to stakeholders operating in building sector and to open new market opportunities. **MATRYCS Modular Toolbox**, will realise a holistic, state-of-the-art AI-empowered framework for decision-support models, data analytics and visualisations for Digital Building Twins and real-life applications aiming to have significant impact on the building sector and its lifecycle, as it will have the ability to be utilised in a wide range of use cases under different perspectives:

- Monitoring and improvement of the energy performance of buildings - **MATRYCS-PERFORMANCE**
- Design facilitation and development of building infrastructure - **MATRYCS-DESIGN**
- Policy making support and policy impact assessment - **MATRYCS-POLICY**
- De-risking of investments in energy efficiency - **MATRYCS-FUND**

Who We Are

	Participant Name	Short Name	Country Code	Logo
1	ENGINEERING – INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA	ENG	IT	
2	NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NTUA	GR	
3	FUNDACION CARTIF	CARTIF	ES	
4	RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN	RWTH	DE	
5	ACCADEMIA EUROPEA DI BOLZANO	EURAC	IT	
6	HOLISTIC IKE	HOLISTIC	GR	
7	COMSENSUS, KOMUNIKACIJE IN SENZORIKA, DOO	COMSENSUS	SL	
8	BLAGOVNO TRGOVINSKI CENTER DD	BTC	SL	
9	PRZEDSIĘBIORSTWO ROBOT ELEWACYJNYCH FASADA SP ZOO	FASADA	PL	
10	MIASTO GDYNIA	GDYNIA	PL	
11	COOPERNICO - COOPERATIVA DE DESENVOLVIMENTO SUSTENTAVEL CRL	COOPERNICO	PT	
12	ASM TERNI SPA	ASM	IT	
13	VEOLIA SERVICIOS LECAM SOCIEDAD ANONIMA UNIPERSONAL	VEOLIA	ES	
14	ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)	ICLEI	DE	
15	ENTE PUBLICO REGIONAL DE LA ENERGIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON	EREN	ES	
16	VIDES INVESTICIJU FONDS SIA	LEIF	LV	
17	COMITE EUROPEEN DE COORDINATION DE L'HABITAT SOCIAL AISBL	HOUSING EUROPE	BE	
18	SEVEN, THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY CENTER Z.U.	SEVEN	CZ	

Contents

1	Introduction	9
2	Website Structure	10
2.1	Structure and content.....	11
2.2	Main elements of the Website tabs	15
2.2.1	Header	15
2.2.2	Footer.....	16
2.3	Home Page.....	16
3	Social Media Channels	19
	Annex I: Visual Identity Guidelines	22

Figures

Figure 1: MATRYCS website Home page.....	10
Figure 2: MATRYCS website map	11
Figure 3: About tab and respective sub-tabs.....	12
Figure 4: Pilots' Application Tab and respective sub-tabs.....	13
Figure 5: Toolbox Tab	13
Figure 6: News and Events Tab	14
Figure 7: MATRYCS website Contact Us link.....	15
Figure 8: MATRYCS website header	16
Figure 9: MATRYCS website footer	16
Figure 10: MATRYCS website slider	17
Figure 11: MATRYCS Welcome banner	17
Figure 12: MATRYCS News & Events section.....	
Figure 13: Communication section	18
Figure 14: Project partners' section	18
Figure 15: MATRYCS Subscribe section	18
Figure 16: Links to MATRYCS Social Media accounts.....	19
Figure 17: MATRYCS Twitter page	19
Figure 18: MATRYCS LinkedIn page	20
Figure 19: MATRYCS Facebook page.....	20
Figure 20: MATRYCS YouTube channel.....	21

Executive Summary

The scope of this report is to describe in detail the design and the content of MATRYCS website which was officially launched in February 2021 (M5). MATRYCS website can be found at the following address: <https://matrycs.eu/>.

Project's website envisions for the effective promotion of MATRYCS concept and outcomes so as to raise awareness and create interest in the field of the big data potential in building sector.

The project's website is a versatile tool for the dissemination and communication activities which are taking place within the project's duration, allowing for the engagement with interested stakeholders and the dissemination of project's outcomes, information related to the project and the consortium partners among interested parties at all levels.

Finally, this report provides useful information about how to navigate through the MATRYCS website and what are the important information expected to be presented along with ways (social media links, subscription to newsletter and contact forms) to communicate with consortium partners.

1 Introduction

Deliverable 8.2 is part of WP8, entitled “Communication, Dissemination and Awareness Creation”, and Task 8.2: Promotional Material and Digital Outreach. The project website is hosted at <https://matrycs.eu/>.

MATRYCS website has been designed on the basis of most recent practices and principles for web design and follows a modern, yet minimalistic and user-friendly approach, presenting in detail the project’s concept and objectives, containing the relevant material and featuring a dedicated section for news and events. All the uploaded material will be easily and freely available. The website follows the visual identity guidelines of MATRYCS (Annex I) and has been designed to be compatible for PC, tablet and phone use.

The aim of MATRYCS website is to present a digestible description of MATRYCS concept and advice for updated MATRYCS activities without using technical language in a user-friendly manner.

The MATRYCS website contains at a minimum level:

- Information about MATRYCS project (concept, methodology, approach, consortium partners, etc.)
- News and Events with relative description
- Library with main resources (outcomes, public deliverables, report, publications, articles, etc.)
- Dissemination material (brochures, videos, infographics, newsletters, press releases, etc.)

The website will be updated periodically (at least once per month and on an ad-hoc basis) to accurately present project progress. The website will run for at least two years after the project ends.

To monitor the website’s traffic and use, and consequently its reach, Google Analytics are used. In order to increase visitor trust and ranking at Google search, a Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate will be applied to the website. Finally, the website practices are compliant with the current EU legislation on personal data and communications-General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

2 Website Structure

The main goals of the MATRYCS website are to:

- Identify MATRYCS concept, objectives, stakeholders, consortium partners, work structure, methodology and expected results.
- Inform about Large scale Pilots' application within the framework of MATRYCS.
- Inform about MATRYCS Toolbox features and give access to it when available.
- Disseminate News and Events including both internal and external activities.
- Disseminate MATRYCS results, namely public deliverables and outputs, publications and promotional material (brochures, videos, infographics, newsletters, press releases, etc.).
- Promote MATRYCS social media accounts and include a newsletter subscription form.

Figure 1: MATRYCS website Home page

The MATRYCS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no.101000158

2.1 Structure and content

The website can be navigated by using the main tabs located at the top part of Home page. Currently, the following items are included in the website:

Figure 2: MATRYCS website map

Home page welcomes visitors to MATRYCS project and has a slideshow with key messages and relevant photos. This slideshow will be frequently updated with news and actions relevant to the project's outcomes. Following, the most recent news and events can be easily accessed in the Home page. Moreover, Home page has the newsletter sign-up section where visitors can subscribe to the newsletter in order to receive the latest MATRYCS news. Finally, links to the social media accounts (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube) have been incorporated in the bottom of the Home page for easy access. Key tabs have been also linked with quick links for easier navigation purposes.

About tab include all the information relating to the project in 5 different sub-tabs:

- The **Concept** sub-tab provides information on the background elements that MATRYCS aims to provide solutions.
- The **Methodology** sub-tab presents briefly the MATRYCS approach to and the main outputs.
- The **Objectives** sub-tab presents the MATRYCS objectives.
- The **Work Structure** sub-tab includes information about the Work Packages under MATRYCS and the linkage between them.
- The **Who we are** sub-tab presents in an accordion-style all the consortium partners with a short description and a link to their websites.

Figure 3: About tab and respective sub-tabs

The **Pilot’s Application** tab is divided in 4 sub-tabs, representing each one of the 4 themes followed by MATRYCS so as to cover different perspectives of the building sector. A short introduction and a graph with all Large Scale Pilots are included. The visitor can navigate in the 4 groups by clicking the sub-tabs and the dedicated icons as well.

- The **Performance** sub-tab includes the description of the LSPs focusing on the monitoring and improvement of the energy performance of buildings.
- The **Design** sub-tab includes the description of the LSPs focusing on the design facilitation and development of building infrastructure.
- The **Policy** sub-tab includes the description of the LSPs focusing on the policy making support and policy impact assessment.
- The **Fund** sub-tab included the description of the LSPs focusing on the de-risking investments in energy efficiency.

Figure 4: Pilots' Application Tab and respective sub-tabs

The **Toolbox** tab is dedicated for the main outcome of MATRYCS, the open, cloud-based data analytics Toolbox. A short description is provided, and an informative message suggests visitors to subscribe to stay update once the Toolbox is ready.

Figure 5: Toolbox Tab

The MATRYCS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no.101000158

The **News and Events** tab is divided in 2 sub-tabs as follows:

- The **MATRYCS News** sub-tab provides news and articles relevant to MATRYCS, announcements of the project and relative events at national and European levels.
- The **MATRYCS Events** sub-tab presents all relevant organisation details of the MATRYCS events, workshops, webinars, etc. including all the informational material.

Figure 6: News and Events Tab

The **Resources Tab** constitutes the place where the visitor can navigate to all useful material such as deliverables, related studies, scientific publications, etc. In particular, the **Results** sub-tab includes all the public deliverables to be freely downloaded, while the **Publications** sub-tab includes all the scientific publications that have been published to promote the MATRYCS outcomes. Finally, the **Related Content** sub-tab includes articles, online reports, etc. relevant to MATRYCS.

The **Communication** tab consists of 4 sub-tabs where the visitor can have access to promotional material, that is, **Newsletters**, **Videos**, **Infographics** and the **Synergies** with projects, initiatives and organisations related to MATRYCS.

Finally, a **Contact Us** link at the bottom of the Home page provides a contact form and comprehensive contact information. This link provides the visitor the capacity to send an email to the consortium. The name, email, adress, subject and message are required. Once this information is provided and the message is sent, it is routed directly to the management team mailing list.

MATRYCS

[About](#)
[Pilots' applications](#)
[Toolbox](#)
[News & Events](#)
[Resources](#)
[Communication](#)

If you have any questions or just want to get in touch, please fill out the form.

First Name
 Last Name

Email
 Subject

Message

Attachment

One file only, 2 MB limit. Allowed types: pdf doc docx ppt pptx.

Figure 7: MATRYCS website Contact Us link

The MATRYCS dissemination strategy foresees to achieve milestones regarding the website in order to ensure success of the dissemination activities and promotion of the MATRYCS project. For this purpose, the Google Analytics (GA) service has been added in the website, offering detailed statistics about the website's traffic and the traffic sources. Google Analytics will provide information on the number of MATRYCS website visitors, as well as the percentage of new visitors, the number of visits and pageviews, allowing us to monitor the website's success as a means of dissemination and information provision.

2.2 Main elements of the Website tabs

The MATRYCS website tabs consist of three basic parts:

- The header on the top
- The footer at the bottom
- The main content in between

2.2.1 Header

The Header, shown in Figure 8, is the place where the MATRYCS logo, the navigation menu and the search bar can be found. It remains constant for all the website tabs and stays pinned always on top, even when the visitor scrolls down in a page.

Figure 8: MATRYCS website header

2.2.2 Footer

The Footer, shown in Figure 9, includes useful information regarding the navigation and the project. The first part includes all social media accounts' links (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube). The second part contains a menu with Quick Links (currently: About, MATRYCS Toolbox, Who we are and Contact us) followed by a statement that the project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme. Finally, the Footer contains a link to the Privacy & Cookies Policy tab.

Figure 9: MATRYCS website footer

2.3 Home Page

The Home page consists of 6 sections apart from the header and footer as shown in Figure 1 (MATRYCS website Home page). It is the first view of the visitors and aims to attract interest and briefly inform about various aspects regarding the project.

1st section: Header

Please see section 2.2.1

2nd section: Slider

The slider is a slideshow where the user can also manually navigate between the slides using the arrows at the top left corner of the slides. The slides are clickable and will direct the visitor to the corresponding section. This section will be frequently updated to highlight the key points of MATRYCS.

Figure 10: MATRYCS website slider

3rd section: Welcome message

A special banner is used to welcome users to MATRYCS with a very brief scope of the project. The arrow on the right bottom redirects the visitor to the Concept sub-tab for further information.

Figure 11: MATRYCS Welcome banner

4th section: News & Events

This section contains links to the most recent and important news and events of MATRYCS. By clicking on an item, the corresponding page is loaded and displayed. The View all News and View all Events buttons redirect the visitor to the News & Event subtabs.

Figure 12: MATRYCS News & Events section

5th section: Communication

This section contains four graphic elements that correspond to the same elements available in the Communication Tab. It offers the visitor the ability to access easily and directly the communication material so as to stay updated for MATRYCS actions. By clicking each of the material, the visitor is redirected to the respective sub-tab.

Figure 13: Communication section

6th section: Project partners

This section presents in a slideshow the project partners. The visitor can get redirected to each of the partners by clicking and highlighting each partner's logo.

Figure 14: Project partners' section

7th section: Subscribe to MATRYCS Newsletter

A Subscribe button can be found in this section which allows the visitor to subscribe and stay updated to MATRYCS news.

Figure 15: MATRYCS Subscribe section

8th section: Footer

Please see section 2.2.2

3 Social Media Channels

Social Media are platforms that are easily accessible to a wide range of people with internet access. They act as a fast and easy way of dissemination tools. In this framework, by exploiting all the assets social media have to offer, they could be very beneficial in successful dissemination of MATRYCS scope, activities and outcomes. Through social media, MATRYCS will take the opportunity to gain wide access to stakeholders from technical to non-technical users, cost-effectively.

MATRYCS social media accounts are listed below:

Twitter: @matrycs_h2020

LinkedIn: MATRYCS

Facebook: matrycs2020

YouTube: MATRYCS H2020

MATRYCS social media accounts will be used throughout the whole duration of the project to engage users and create traffic to the website. Posts and tweets may include announcements for events and outcomes, reports and publications, activities and dissemination material and interventions in conferences, workshops etc.

The Social Media banner, shown in Figure 16, stays static in all tabs of MATRYCS website.

Figure 16: Links to MATRYCS Social Media accounts

The following figures present the MATRYCS social media accounts.

Figure 17: MATRYCS Twitter page

Figure 18: MATRYCS LinkedIn page

Figure 19: MATRYCS Facebook page

The MATRYCS project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no.101000158

Figure 20: MATRYCS YouTube channel

Annex I: Visual Identity Guidelines

Colour Palette

 HEX: #14487C RGB: 20, 72, 124 CMYK: 99, 78, 26, 10	
 HEX: #72BF56 RGB: 114, 191, 86 CMYK: 59, 0, 88, 0	
 HEX: #3A3F49 RGB: 58, 63, 73 CMYK: 75, 65, 52, 42	

Typography

Font: Segoe UI

Bold: **The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog**

Regular: The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog

SemiLight: THE QUICK BROWN FOX JUMPS OVER THE LAZY DOG

Italic: *1234567890*

Logo

